

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Bhideshwari, a new rice variety for rainfed wetland areas in Nepal

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Bhideshwari (IET1444), obtained through a TN1 / CO 29 cross in India, was introduced in Nepal through the International Upland Rice Yield Nursery in 1975. In tests under wetland conditions, it averaged 3.6 t/ha at 6 irrigated sites and 3.5 t/ha at 7 rainfed sites. Under rainfed dryland conditions at 3 sites over 3 years, it averaged

2.7 t/ha. In farmers' fields, it averaged 3.2 t/ha.

Disease resistance was high, with ratings (Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale) of 3 for bacterial blight, 5 for brown spot, and 3 for blast. Bhideshwari matures in 105 days and is 85 cm high. Protein-content is 8%.

The variety release committee of the Department of Agriculture, Nepal, has released Bhideshwari for areas at altitudes of 914 m under varying growth conditions. Because almost all previous varieties were recommended for irrigated conditions and high inputs, a large area is expected to be planted to Bhideshwari in the future. ■

Induced rice mutants in Haryana

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Using doses of physical (r rays) and chemical (DES, EMS) mutagens, singly and in combination, we rectified some

of the genetic defects in three most commonly cultivated rices: Basmati 370, Jhona 349, and IR8. Plant progeny performance of 40 mutants led to the selection of 2 mutants of Basmati that are earlier maturing and higher yielding than the initial line (see table). But grain fineness is much reduced.

Two Jhona mutants with much

Characteristics of rice mutants in Haryana.^a

	Shoot ht (cm)	Maturity in days	Grain yield (g)	Grain fineness (length:breadth)	Protein content (%)
Basmati 370 (control)	147.1 ± 0.67	148.98 ± 0.91	16.1 ± 0.36	3.61 ± 0.02	7.6 ± 0.08
Bm3	122.1 ± 0.90	132.15 ± 0.95	21.4 ± 0.55	2.82 ± 0.01	7.4 ± 0.05
Bm4	116.7 ± 0.59	130.69 ± 0.88	21.3 ± 0.52	2.76 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.04
CD at 5% level	4.79	6.34	1.25	0.05	0.05
Jhona 349 (control)	132.5 ± 0.54	125.16 ± 0.71	20.4 ± 0.59	3.00 ± 0.02	7.3 ± 0.04
Jm2	128.7 ± 0.69	124.72 ± 0.82	22.8 ± 0.61	3.51 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.09
Jm3	137.2 ± 0.70	123.29 ± 0.75	20.6 ± 0.61	3.52 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.08
CD at 5% level	4.69	5.78	1.25	0.05	0.06
IR8 (control)	87.8 ± 0.04	150.90 ± 1.38	20.6 ± 0.36	2.38 ± 0.01	7.1 ± 0.04
IRm1	118.2 ± 0.80	124.19 ± 1.85	22.6 ± 0.36	2.82 ± 0.02	8.2 ± 0.06
IRm6	85.7 ± 0.40	131.68 ± 1.48	20.8 ± 0.26	2.62 ± 0.01	8.7 ± 0.05
CD at 5% level	5.43	7.42	1.03	0.04	0.07

^aMean values of 360 plants, M₅-M₇ generations. ±: standard error.